

I. Logical Proof of the Existence of God:

DEFINITION: God is the entity for which it does not hold true that its existence is caused by another entity/ not only by itself.

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II. Logical Proof that ("Unadulterated") Materialism is Fallacious:

("Unadulterated") materialism claims (to the extent it comprehends its own claims) that we, as conscious beings, consist of dead, inanimate matter, organized to an extreme degree - a localized in space 'hyper-defeat' of entropy (And indeed, this is what happens! - referring to the entropy aspect). Our consciousness (in contrast to dead, inanimate matter) is, according to materialism, merely a supervening, emergent property.

The issue, however, is this: for an emergent property to arise within a system, something related to it must exist in every individual component participating in the system - something that, logically, can lead to it at the macro-system level (in our case, dear reader, consider the components as the building blocks of matter, and the system as... us). Something that, using an allegory driven by Mathematics, is ontologically "topologically equivalent" to the final outcome of - maximum order- (our) anti-entropy.

In short: dead, inanimate matter (no matter how neatly arranged and interacting with itself) produces consciousness ex nihilo [out of non-being] according to materialists (while otherwise, I imagine, they strictly accept the scientific principle that rejects anything appearing or being generated ex nihilo...).

III. Logical Proof that Virtue Does Not Exist:

Let us assume that Virtue exists: Since God is just, He will reward it. Ultimately, if God does not 'point us' toward it in some way, then why is it Virtue? However, if the meaning of Virtue is solely the gain of the virtuous individual (or the detriment of the wicked), then, dear reader (allow me the use of the following verb), I feel that this cannot truly constitute Virtue with a capital 'V'.

We therefore have the following two cases:

- a) The Virtue of x does good to y.
- b) (OR/AND:) The Virtue of the conscious entity x brings the conscious entity y into existence.

Case (a) is rejected, because God, being just, rewards/punishes everyone individually.

Case (b) is rejected (?), because God is immutable; if we assume that had x shown greater virtue/less wickedness, they would have brought y into existence (or, in any case, would have brought more existence into existence), this implies that the Creator "throttles" His Creative Energy - meaning He creates less being/consciousness, if I engage in misdeeds.

(Furthermore, shouldn't God exhaust His Creative energy (if not, why? – is He bored?), so that it constitutes, in magnitude, the supreme infinity? Within this infinity, however, by definition, nothing measurable can be added or subtracted.)

(Note on Ontology: I equate existence with consciousness because: Consciousness without existence obviously does not exist, but neither does existence without consciousness make any sense whatsoever (How can we say that something exists unless it is perceived/experienced by some consciousness?).)